

VIBRATION FATIGUE ANALYSIS OF CIRCUMFERENTIALLY NOTCHED SPECIMENS UNDER COUPLED MULTIAXIAL RANDOM VIBRATION ENVIRONMENTS

Zhengbo Luo^{a,b}, Sabrina Vantadori^c, Camilla Ronchei^d, Andrea Carpinteri^c, Huaihai Chen^{a*}

^aState Key laboratory of Mechanics and Control of Mechanical Structures, College of Aerospace Engineering, Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Nanjing 210016, China

^bState-owned Wuhu Machinery Factory, Wuhu Anhui 241007, China

^bDepartment of Civil and Environmental Engineering & Architecture, University of Parma, Parco Area delle Scienze 181/A, Parma 43124, Italy

^cDepartment of Civil Engineering, University of Calabria, via Pietro Bucci, 87036 Arcavacata di Rende (CS), Italy

ABSTRACT

The time-domain critical plane-based Carpinteri et al. criterion and the Theory of the Critical Distance are here combined together so as to propose a novel procedure for vibration fatigue analysis of circumferentially notched specimens subjected to coupled multiaxial random vibration environments. A novel metallic testing equipment is specially devised for notched specimen, meanwhile biaxial random vibration environment fatigue test is specially implemented on notched specimen in order to investigate how both coherence and phase shift between the ASD auto-spectral density functions in different directions influence the specimen fatigue life. The location of the verification point where to perform the fatigue damage estimation is determined by applying both the point method and the Carpinteri et al. criterion (for damage evaluation). The obtained results prove that the proposed procedure can provide satisfactory fatigue life estimations.

Keywords: Coherence; Multiaxial loading; Notched specimen; Phase shift; Time-domain.

1. INTRODUCTION

Engineering structural components under in-service conditions often experience complex random vibration environments¹⁻³. Therefore, the vibration fatigue analysis of such components becomes

an interesting research topic in the scientific community⁴⁻¹².

Random vibration environment tests can be implemented in the laboratory so as to simulate the complex vibration environments that structural components have to endure in reality¹³. In the last decades, the uniaxial random vibration testing was the only type of excitation test method because uniaxial shaker tables were the only available excitation sources. However, such a type of testing has two potential limitations:

- (a) Structural components can be excited only in a single direction under random vibration;
- (b) The influence of coupling relationships between the excitations in different directions on both complex random stress states as well as unexpected vibration fatigue failure modes of structural components cannot be taken into account under uniaxial random vibration.

Consequently, in order to recreate the multiaxial characteristics of real random vibration environments in the laboratory, the sequential uniaxial random vibration testing has been created as the standard vibration environment test method^{14,15}. In sequential uniaxial random vibration tests, the structural components being examined are rotated along three orthogonal directions sequentially, and a uniaxial shaker table is used to excite the structural components in each direction for a period of time. However, such a testing still has a significant limitation, that is, it cannot be used to simulate the real vibration environment with different coupling relationships between the excitations in different directions.

In the recent years, benefiting from the capability of advanced test facilities and multiple-input multiple-output control techniques, the multiaxial random vibration testing which employs a triaxial shaker table has become the most advanced test method¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Such a testing has great advantages in replicating the in-service conditions, since it simultaneously excites the examined

structural component in three orthogonal directions.

At present, the research on fatigue under multiaxial random vibration environments is still an open challenge, and methods to predict fatigue lives of structural components under such a loading condition are encouraged to be formulated since they are cheaper and less time-consuming than experimental tests. Complex multiaxial stress states may be induced by various coupled multiaxial random vibration environments. There are various multiaxial criteria available in the literature for fatigue analysis of *smooth structural components* in case of such multiaxial stress states¹⁹⁻²¹. However, fatigue analysis of *notched structural components* under multiaxial stress states is still an interesting research topic to be explored. In the 1940s to 1950s, Neuber²² and Peterson²³ firstly presented the concept of critical distance so as to predict the fatigue limits of notched structural components. Based on their fundamental works, Tanaka²⁴, Lazzarin et al.²⁵ and Taylor²⁶ established analytical mathematical relationships between the El Haddad's intrinsic crack length²⁷ and the critical distance. The Theory of the Critical Distance (TCD) by Taylor was successfully utilized to predict high-cycle fatigue strengths of structural components weakened by various types of notches^{26,28,29}. According to the assumption of the TCD, a linear-elastic constitutive relationship can be used to simulate the mechanical behaviour of metallic materials, meanwhile a linear-elastic FE analysis can be performed to evaluate the local stress field near the stress raisers being examined. The TCD postulates that a notched structural component appears fatigue limit condition either when the normal stress at a given distance from the notch tip (point method) is equal to the material uniaxial fatigue limit σ_{af} of smooth components or when the averaged value of the normal stress (computed along a line, or an area or a volume) is equal to σ_{af} . More precisely, such an averaged value can be computed (a) over a

line (line method) or (b) over a semi-circular area (area method) or (c) over a semi-sphere (volume method) ahead of the notch tip. These parameter values (i.e. the given distance, the line length, the circle radius and the sphere radius) are all related to the material characteristic length, which can be determined through the EI Haddad et al. empirical law²⁷:

$$L = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\frac{K_{th}}{\sigma_{af}} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

where K_{th} denotes the stress intensity factor threshold, measured at the same loading ratio used for determining the material uniaxial fatigue limit σ_{af} .

In the current research study, an extension of the time-domain critical plane-based Carpinteri et al. criterion³⁰ is proposed for vibration fatigue analysis of circumferentially notched specimens under complex multiaxial stress states, implementing the point method in the above criterion. To experimentally achieve the above stress state, a novel testing equipment installed on a triaxial shaker table is designed by making some changes with respect to that described in Refs [11,12].

The above equipment is employed to implement biaxial random vibration environment fatigue test in order to examine how both coherence and phase shift between excitations in different directions influence the notched specimen fatigue life. Then, the time-domain Carpinteri et al. criterion is employed to validate such an experimental campaign.

The novelty of the present paper concerns two aspects: (i) application of the above criterion to notched structural components, by also implementing the point method of the TCD, and (ii) experimental tests carried out under a stress state consisting of two normal stresses together with a shear one (so far, the case of only one normal stress together with a shear one has been examined³⁰⁻³³). Note that, among the different TCD formalisations, the point method is here adopted since, in presence of a complex loading, it is easier to determine the stress state at a single

point rather than to perform average procedures according to the line, area and volume methods.

The framework of the present paper is described as follows. In Section 2, some basic concepts of the structural dynamic analysis and the criterion employed for multiaxial notch fatigue analysis are discussed. In Section 3, the experimental campaign (tested specimens, adopted procedure, and obtained results) is summarized. In Section 4, a modal analysis of the testing equipment with the specimen is presented by means of the FE approach. In Section 5, the time-domain Carpinteri et al. criterion is employed to the above experimental data. In Section 6 and Section 7, the obtained results are discussed and some conclusions are drawn, respectively.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Description of multiaxial random vibration environments

Multiaxial random vibration tests of structural components can be carried out by using a triaxial shaker system. Such a system can provide outputs of various coupled time-domain acceleration random base excitations in three orthogonal directions.

In random vibration environment fatigue tests, the one-sided Power Spectral Density (PSD) matrix of the random excitation is usually used to describe the time-domain acceleration random base excitations provided by the triaxial shaker system:

$$\mathbf{G}_a(f) = \begin{pmatrix} G_{xx}(f) & G_{xy}(f) & G_{xz}(f) \\ G_{yx}(f) & G_{yy}(f) & G_{yz}(f) \\ G_{zx}(f) & G_{zy}(f) & G_{zz}(f) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where f is the frequency, $\mathbf{G}_a(f)$ ($3 \times 3 \times n$) is a positive Hermitian matrix, that has to be considered for all the f values (whose number is equal to n) within the acceleration excitation

frequency range. The diagonal elements $G_{kk}(f)$ and the non-diagonal elements $G_{kl}(f)$ ($k \neq l$) denote the auto-spectral density (ASD) functions of the time-domain acceleration base excitations and the cross-spectral density (CSD) functions between the time-domain acceleration base excitations, respectively.

The corresponding ASD functions can be used to define the CSD functions by specifying the coherence and phase shift. In other words, the CSD function $G_{kl}(f)$ can be specifically defined as follows:

$$G_{kl}(f) = |G_{kl}(f)| e^{-j\theta_{kl}(f)} = \sqrt{\gamma_{kl}^2(f) G_{kk}(f) G_{ll}(f)} e^{-j\theta_{kl}(f)} \quad (3)$$

where j denotes the imaginary unit. $\gamma_{kl}^2(f)$ and $\theta_{kl}(f)$ denote coherence and phase shift between the corresponding ASD functions, respectively.

2.2. Basic concepts of structural dynamic analysis

In case of acceleration base excitations, structural dynamic analysis can be performed in order to derive the dynamic stress responses of structural components. Meanwhile, based on the idea of the finite element method (FEM), the discrete multi-degree-of-freedom (MDOF) systems can be used to represent such structural components. In the case of dynamic force excitations, the equilibrium equations of the viscous damped MDOF system are written as follows³⁴:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{F}(t) \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{C} denote the structural mass, stiffness and damping matrices, respectively. Moreover, $\mathbf{u}(t)$ and $\mathbf{F}(t)$ denote the absolute displacement vector of the MDOF system and the force excitation vector as the input to the MDOF system, respectively.

In order to decouple the differential equations of the viscous damped MDOF system in Eq. (4),

the modal decomposition needs to be introduced. The physical coordinate vector $\mathbf{u}(t)$ can be linked with the modal coordinate vector $\mathbf{q}(t)$ by the modal decomposition³⁵:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \Phi \mathbf{q}(t) \quad (5)$$

where Φ is the displacement modal shape matrix which is composed of the eigenvectors.

Using the modal decomposition, the differential equations of the viscous damped MDOF system in Eq. (4) can be rewritten as follows:

$$\Phi^T \mathbf{M} \Phi \ddot{\mathbf{q}}(t) + \Phi^T \mathbf{C} \Phi \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t) + \Phi^T \mathbf{K} \Phi \mathbf{q}(t) = \Phi^T \mathbf{F}(t) \quad (6)$$

where the symbol ‘T’ represents the transpose operation.

The frequency-domain form of Eq. (6) can be expressed as:

$$\left(-\omega^2 \Phi^T \mathbf{M} \Phi + j\omega \Phi^T \mathbf{C} \Phi + \Phi^T \mathbf{K} \Phi \right) \mathbf{q}(\omega) = \Phi^T \mathbf{F}(\omega) \quad (7)$$

where ω is the pulsation.

The MDOF system is assumed to be a proportional damping model. In this way, Eq. (7) is decoupled as:

$$\left(-\omega^2 m_r + j\omega c_r + k_r \right) q_r(\omega) = f_r(\omega) \quad (8)$$

where m_r, k_r, c_r and f_r denote the r -th modal mass, modal stiffness, modal damping and modal force excitation, respectively. Once the modal responses are computed, the physical responses can be obtained from the superposition of modal responses.

The displacement frequency response function (FRF) matrix $\mathbf{H}_d(\omega)$ of the MDOF system under force excitations is computed as follows:

$$\mathbf{H}_d(\omega) = \sum_{r=1}^N \frac{\phi_r \phi_r^T}{k_r - \omega^2 m_r + i\omega c_r} \quad (9)$$

where N denotes the number of degrees of freedom of the MDOF system, and ϕ_r denotes the r -th column vector of the displacement modal shape matrix Φ .

The dynamic stress responses of the MDOF system are given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s(t) = \boldsymbol{\Phi}^s \mathbf{q}(t) = \sum_{r=1}^N \boldsymbol{\phi}_r^s q_r(t) \quad (10)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s(t)$ is the stress vector process, and $\boldsymbol{\Phi}^s$ is the stress modal shape matrix. $q_r(t)$ and $\boldsymbol{\phi}_r^s$ are the r -th modal coordinate of the modal coordinate vector $\mathbf{q}(t)$ and the r -th column vector of the stress modal shape matrix $\boldsymbol{\Phi}^s$, respectively.

The stress FRF matrix $\mathbf{H}_s(\omega)$ of the MDOF system under force excitations can be calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{H}_s(\omega) = \sum_{r=1}^N \frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}_r^s \boldsymbol{\phi}_r^{sT}}{k_r - \omega^2 m_r + i\omega c_r} \quad (11)$$

However, the triaxial shaker system provides the acceleration random base excitations instead of the force excitations in the random vibration environment fatigue test. Consequently, the stress FRF matrix $\mathbf{H}_s(\omega)$ in Eq. (11) cannot be directly used. In the case of acceleration base excitations, the equilibrium equations of the viscous damped MDOF systems are written in the following expression³⁶:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{v}}(t) + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{v}}(t) + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{v}(t) = -\mathbf{M}\mathbf{T}\ddot{\mathbf{w}}(t) \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{v}(t) = \mathbf{u}(t) - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{w}(t)$ and $\ddot{\mathbf{w}}(t)$ denote the relative displacement vector and the acceleration random base excitation vector, respectively, and \mathbf{T} denotes a constant transfer function matrix.

In a similar way, in the case of acceleration random base excitations, the stress FRF matrix $\mathbf{H}_{as}(\omega)$ of the MDOF system is deduced:

$$\mathbf{H}_{as}(\omega) = -\mathbf{H}_s(\omega)\mathbf{M}\mathbf{T} \quad (13)$$

In practical applications, the stress FRF matrix $\mathbf{H}_{as}(\omega)$ of the MDOF system can be determined via the frequency response analysis in the FE software. The relationship between the

one-sided response stress PSD matrix, $\mathbf{G}_s(f)$, and the one-sided PSD matrix of the random excitation, $\mathbf{G}_a(f)$, can be described by the following expression:

$$\mathbf{G}_s(f) = \mathbf{H}_{as}^*(f) \mathbf{G}_a(f) \mathbf{H}_{as}^T(f) \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{as}(f) = \mathbf{H}_{as}(\omega/2\pi)$, and the symbol ‘*’ represents the complex conjugate operation.

For a random stress vector process $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s(t) = [\sigma_{xx}(t), \sigma_{yy}(t), \sigma_{zz}(t), \sigma_{xy}(t), \sigma_{yz}(t), \sigma_{zx}(t)]^T$, the corresponding one-sided stress PSD matrix, $\mathbf{G}_s(f)$, is given as follows:

$$\mathbf{G}_s(f) = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11}(f) & \cdots & G_{16}(f) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ G_{61}(f) & \cdots & G_{66}(f) \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

In order to describe the degree of proportionality between stress components, a stress covariance matrix, \mathbf{C}_v , can be introduced as follows:

$$\mathbf{C}_v = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & \cdots & C_{16} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ C_{61} & \cdots & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

where the diagonal term C_{ii} and the non-diagonal term C_{ij} ($i \neq j$) denote the variance of the stress component and the covariance between the stress components, respectively. More precisely, those diagonal and non-diagonal terms in covariance matrix \mathbf{C}_v can be computed as follows:

$$C_{ii} = \text{Var}(s_i(t)) = \int_0^{+\infty} G_{ii}(f) df \quad (17)$$

$$C_{ij} = \text{Cov}(s_i(t), s_j(t)) = \int_0^{+\infty} \text{real}[G_{ij}(f)] df \quad (18)$$

Finally, correlation coefficient can be used to quantify the stress component non-proportionality. Such a coefficient r_{ij} can be defined as follows:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{|C_{ij}|}{\sqrt{C_{ii} C_{jj}}} \quad (19)$$

2.3. The time-domain Carpinteri et al. criterion for smooth structural components

Based on the well-known classification standard of multiaxial fatigue criteria, the time-domain Carpinteri et al. criterion³⁰ is classified as the critical plane-based criteria. Such a criterion has been proposed for fatigue analysis of *smooth metallic structural components* under variable and random fatigue loadings³⁰⁻³³, when the material sensitivity to non-proportional loading can be considered negligible.

Firstly, the material sensitivity to non-proportional loading has to be examined. The ratio of material fatigue strengths at a given number of loading cycles related to fully reversed shear stress over fully reversed normal stress, $\tau_{af,-1} / \sigma_{af,-1}$, is used to such an aim. As a matter of fact, according to Papadopoulos' statement³⁷, when $\tau_{af,-1} / \sigma_{af,-1} > 1/\sqrt{3}$, the material shows a negligible decrease of the experimental fatigue strength under non-proportional loading.

A linear-elastic FE analysis approach can be applied to compute the stress response PSD matrix, $\mathbf{G}_s(f)$ (shown in Eq. (15)), at the verification point, P_{cr} , of the structural component, and the time-domain randomization method^{11,16} can be employed to generate the stress time-domain sequences at the verification point P_{cr} .

Following the present criterion, the multiaxial fatigue life prediction is mainly divided into three steps: the first step is to locate the critical plane orientation; the second step is to perform the multiaxial cycle counting procedure of the normal stress and the shear stress components acting on the critical plane and to obtain an equivalent stress amplitude series; the final step is to evaluate the total fatigue damage by applying the Palmgren-Miner rule.

To determine the orientation of the critical plane at point P_{cr} , the averaged principal Euler angles $\hat{\varphi}, \hat{\theta}$ and $\hat{\phi}$ have to be calculated by performing the weighted average operation of instantaneous Euler angles (i.e. $\varphi(t), \theta(t)$ and $\phi(t)$), through a weight function $V(t)$ in the

observation time interval T :

$$\hat{\varphi} = \frac{1}{V} \int_0^T \varphi(t)V(t)dt \quad \hat{\theta} = \frac{1}{V} \int_0^T \theta(t)V(t)dt \quad \hat{\phi} = \frac{1}{V} \int_0^T \phi(t)V(t)dt \quad (20)$$

being $V = \int_0^T V(t)dt$. The weight functions $V(t)$ can be expressed as follows:

$$V(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \sigma_1(t) < \sigma_{1,\max} \\ 1 & \text{if } \sigma_1(t) \geq \sigma_{1,\max} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

where $\sigma_1(t)$ is the instantaneous maximum principal stress, and $\sigma_{1,\max}$ is the maximum value of $\sigma_1(t)$ during the observation interval.

The Cartesian coordinate frame $\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}$ with its origin in P_{cr} can be defined through the above-mentioned weighted averaged Euler angles $\hat{\varphi}, \hat{\theta}, \hat{\phi}$, which denote three counter-clockwise rotations about three axes (i.e. the Z-axis, Y'-axis and $\hat{1}$ -axis) sequentially.

Then, the critical plane orientation and the averaged principal axes can be correlated to each other through the off-angle δ defined in the principal plane $\hat{1}\hat{3}$, which is the angle between the averaged principal axis $\hat{1}$ and the unit vector \mathbf{n} perpendicular to critical plane. An empirical formula of the off-angle δ can be written as:

$$\delta = \frac{3\pi}{8} \left[1 - \left(\frac{\tau_{af,-1}}{\sigma_{af,-1}} \right)^2 \right] \quad (22)$$

where δ is expressed in radians. Moreover, $\tau_{af,-1}$ and $\sigma_{af,-1}$ are the material fatigue strength, at a given number N_0 of loading cycles, under fully reversed shear stress and under fully reversed normal stress, respectively. Note that Eq. (22) is valid when the ratio $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$ ranges between $1/\sqrt{3}$ and 1. The off-angle δ is assumed to be equal to 0 for $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1} > 1$, whereas it is assumed to be equal to $\pi/4$ for $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1} < 1/\sqrt{3}$ (for more details, see Ref. [32]).

Subsequently, let us consider the critical plane through the given point P_{cr} , and the attached Cartesian coordinate frame uvw (with its origin in P_{cr}), where the u -axis is the intersection

between the critical plane and the plane defined by \mathbf{n} and Z-axis, and the v -axis forms a right-handed system together with the u - and w -axis. The stress vector $\mathbf{S}_n(t)$ acting on the critical plane at point P_{cr} can be computed in the following expression:

$$\mathbf{S}_n(t) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(t) \cdot \mathbf{n} \quad (23)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(t)$ denotes the stress tensor acting at the verification point P_{cr} .

The normal stress vector $\mathbf{N}(t)$ and the shear stress vector $\mathbf{R}(t)$ acting on the critical plane can be computed as:

$$\mathbf{N}(t) = (\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{S}_n(t)) \mathbf{n} \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{R}(t) = \mathbf{S}_n(t) - \mathbf{N}(t) \quad (25)$$

Then, the multiaxial cycle counting procedure of the stress components acting on the critical plane is here described. Basing on the sampling theorem, stress component vectors $\mathbf{N}(t)$ and $\mathbf{R}(t)$ can be regarded as the discrete variables when the sampling frequency is greater than twice of the highest frequency component of the applied stress time-domain sequences. The scalar value of the normal stress vector $\mathbf{N}(t)$ is treated as the main cycle counting variable, while the scalar value of the shear stress vector $\mathbf{R}(t)$ (defined through two shear stress components $R_u(t)$ and $R_v(t)$) is treated as the auxiliary cycle counting variable. Firstly, a peak/valley sequence N_j^* can be derived by eliminating the time instants corresponding to non-extreme values of the original sequence N_i . The same time instants are eliminated in the original sequence \mathbf{R}_i and a new sequence \mathbf{R}_j^* can be obtained by means of a reduction procedure which preserves the maximum shear stress amplitudes. Details of such a reduction procedure are reported in Ref. [30].

Then, the rain-flow counting (RFC) procedure is applied to the peak/valley sequence N_j^* . The maximum normal stress value $N_{\max,k}^*$ can be determined for each k -th reversal, and the

corresponding shear stress amplitude $R_{a,k}^*$ can be deduced on the basis of the sequence \mathbf{R}_j^* . For the k -th reversal, the equivalent stress amplitude $\sigma_{eq,a,k}$ is expressed as follows:

$$\sigma_{eq,a,k} = \sqrt{\left(N_{max,k}^*\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\tau_{af,-1}}\right)^2 \left(R_{a,k}^*\right)^2} \quad (26)$$

Finally, the Palmgren-Miner rule is employed for the equivalent stress amplitude $\sigma_{eq,a,k}$, and the total fatigue damage is computed in the following formula:

$$D(T) = \sum_{k=1}^K D_k \quad (27)$$

where the notation K represents the number of reversals in the sequence N_j^* .

In Eq. (27), D_k is expressed as follows:

$$D_k = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2N_0 \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\sigma_{eq,a,k}}\right)^{\frac{1}{k_{axi}}}} & \text{if } \sigma_{eq,a,k} \geq s\sigma_{af,-1} \\ 0 & \text{if } \sigma_{eq,a,k} < s\sigma_{af,-1} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

where k_{axi} and s denote the fully-reversed uniaxial fatigue curve's inverse slope and the safety coefficient ($0 \leq s \leq 1$), respectively.

2.4. Extension of the time-domain multiaxial criterion to notched structural components

Now an extension of the time-domain criterion previously presented implementing the point method is proposed for vibration fatigue analysis of *notched metallic structural components* under complex multiaxial random fatigue loading. The proposed procedure for the fatigue life evaluation is mainly divided into three steps: (1) determination of the hot spot in the notched

metallic structural component; (2) determination of the verification point, P_{cr} , by means of the TCD point method; (3) computation of the fatigue damage and fatigue life at P_{cr} by applying the criterion presented in Section 2.3.

Under plane stress/strain condition, a general traction-free notch surface is considered for the following notch fatigue problem (**Figure 1**). It is assumed that the hot spot H is the material point experiencing the maximum value of the maximum principal stress $\sigma_1(t)$, determined, for instance, through a FE analysis.

Figure 1.

The TCD point method is employed to determine the location of the verification point P_{cr} . To such an aim, let us consider a segment emanating from H and identified by an orientation angle α (positive for counter clockwise rotation), measured with respect to the direction perpendicular to the notch profile.

According to the point method, the material point P_{cr} where to perform the fatigue damage evaluation is on a semicircle with H as the centre and $L/2$ as the radius. To determine the location of P_{cr} , the time-domain Carpinteri et al. criterion (Section 2.3) has to be used to each point of such a semicircle, the stress state input data being determined by employing the time-domain randomization method^{11,16} (Section 2.2). At each point, the total damage is computed through Eq. (27). The material point, providing the maximum damage D_{max} , is considered as the verification point P_{cr} .

Finally, the structural component's fatigue life T_{cal} can be computed as follows:

$$T_{cal} = \frac{D_{cr} \cdot T}{D_{max}} \quad (29)$$

where D_{cr} is the critical damage value, assumed to be equal to 1, and T is the observation time interval.

3. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN

3.1. Novel test equipment

In the present study, a novel test equipment (**Figure 2**), installed on the triaxial shaker table – model G-6080-3HT-20 (**Figure 3**), is employed to perform biaxial random vibration environment fatigue tests.

Figure 2

Figure 3

The configuration of such an equipment is similar to that presented in Refs [11,12], and is composed by two lateral thin plates and a novel T-clamping component (**Figure 2(a)**). The equipment is installed on the triaxial table through a baseplate and fixtures (**Figure 2(b)**).

A triaxial accelerometer (No. 1 in **Figure 2(b)**), mounted on the shaker table centre, is employed to measure the acceleration time signals in real time, and is combined with a multiaxial vibration controller to realise the close-loop control. Two additional triaxial accelerometers (No. 2 and 3 in **Figure 2(b)**), mounted on the specimen end and T-clamping component end, respectively, are applied to measure the acceleration responses in real time, which are employed to determine the modal frequency.

As shown in **Figure 4**, the specimen is the circumferentially U-notched cylindrical bar. The stress concentration factor is equal to 1.65 for bending, and 1.38 for torsion.

Figure 4

3.2. Materials of specimens and T-clamping component

The notched specimens are made from 2024-T4 aluminum alloy and **Table 1** displays the mechanical and related fatigue properties of such a material¹¹.

Table 1

The material used for the T-clamping component is 45 steel, with a Young's modulus of 210 GPa, a density of 7850 kg/m³ and a Poisson's ratio of 0.27.

3.3. Modal testing

A modal testing on the novel testing equipment (with the notched specimen included) is performed so as to determine the frequency range of acceleration excitations. The modal testing results are reported in **Table 2**. According to the modal testing results, the frequency range of $\mathbf{G}_a(f)$ is defined as 50-200 Hz.

Table 2

An example of the profiles of the $\mathbf{G}_a(f)$ diagonal terms, i.e. the ASD functions of the

time-domain acceleration random base excitations, is shown in **Figure 5**, for both Y- (**Figure 5(a)**) and Z-direction (**Figure 5(b)**). As can be observed, such profiles are characterised by flat spectra.

Figure 5

By plotting both the coherence and the phase shift between the ASD functions in the above directions against frequency, it can be remarked that they remain unchanged in the frequency range 50-200 Hz (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6

The acceleration time-domain signals corresponding to the acceleration excitation PSD matrix $\mathbf{G}_a(f)$ are displayed in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7

3.4. Biaxial random vibration environment fatigue testing

Twelve loading cases for biaxial random vibration environment fatigue tests and two loading cases for uniaxial ones (that is, pure bending and torsion) are examined (**Table 3**).

Table 3

The experimental fatigue life for each test is also listed in **Table 3**. Such a life is the time needed to have a 5% decrease in the first order modal frequency³⁸. The averaged experimental fatigue life $T_{exp,ave}$ is also shown in Table 3.

4. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

4.1. Numerical model

A linear-elastic numerical model of the testing equipment (including the notched specimen) is used to perform the FE analysis. The FE model, created by Ansys 14.5 Workbench 15, of the testing equipment (**Figure 8**) is composed of 59112 hexahedral elements and 1860 pentahedral elements with a total number of nodes equal to 64664. In the process of meshing generation, the grid encryption operation is performed on the notch root and, after executing a convergence analysis, the minimum FE size is set as 0.03 millimeter.

Figure 8

4.2. Modal analysis

Numerical modal results of the testing equipment can be determined by modal analysis with the FEM (**Figure 9**). The large mass method is employed to simulate the complex multi-axial random vibration environments provided by a triaxial shaker system.

Figure 9

Combining the modes and the experimental modal damping ratios, modal superposition approach is applied to obtain the structural acceleration and stress responses. **Figure 10(a)** shows the comparison between numerical and experimental acceleration FRFs (normalised with respect to gravitational acceleration, g) at the T-clamping component end (accelerometer No. 3) under the Y-direction's acceleration random base excitation, whereas **Figure 10(b)** shows the comparison between numerical and experimental acceleration FRFs (normalised with respect to gravitational acceleration, g) at the specimen end (accelerometer No. 2) under the Z-direction's acceleration

random base excitation. In comparison with experiments, the relative error is about 3% for bending mode and about 1.2% for torsional mode.

Figure 10

The analysis shows that the stress state of the notched specimen is characterized by two “bending” normal stresses, $s_1(t)$ and $s_2(t)$ (produced by bending mode) and by a “torsional” shear stress $s_4(t)$ (produced by torsional mode).

5. EVALUATION OF FATIGUE LIFE

The material examined can be considered insensitive to non-proportional loading. As a matter of fact, $\tau_{af,-1} / \sigma_{af,-1}$ is greater than $1/\sqrt{3}$, being such a ratio equal to 0.72 (see **Table 1**).

As is discussed in Section 2.4, the location of the hot spot H is at the notch root (**Figure 1**). The segment orientation α is made to vary from -90° to 90° (with an angular increment equal to 10°), and L is equal to 0.36 millimeter³⁹.

Note that, for the purpose of the accumulative damage computation, the time histories of $s_1(t)$, $s_2(t)$ and $s_4(t)$ are computed by employing: (i) the FE model described in Section 4; (ii) the stress response PSD matrix $\mathbf{G}_s(f)$; (iii) the time-domain randomization method^{11,16}.

The comparison between calculated fatigue life T_{cal} and averaged experimental fatigue life $T_{exp,ave}$ is displayed in **Figure 11(a)**, where the solid line demonstrates $T_{cal} = T_{exp,ave}$, the dashed line and dash-dot line demonstrate $T_{cal}/T_{exp,ave} = 0.5-2$ and $T_{cal}/T_{exp,ave} = 0.33-3$, respectively. Note that 57% of the calculated results are into the scatter band of two times, whereas 93% of them are into the scatter band of three times.

Figure 11

Moreover, by evaluating the accuracy of the proposed criterion by means of the mean square error⁴⁰, T_{RMS} , the value of such an error is equal to 2.25.

In addition, biaxial random vibration environment fatigue tests available in the literature^{11,12}, performed by using an equipment similar to that here employed, are also examined by means of the proposed procedure. **Figure 11(b)** displays the averaged experimental fatigue life $T_{exp,ave}$ plotted against the calculated one T_{cal} . It is shown that 70% of calculated results are into the scatter band of two times, whereas 90% of calculated results are into the scatter band of three times.

In such a case, T_{RMS} is equal to 2.12.

6. DISCUSSION

As is shown in **Table 4**, coherence and phase shift between the ASD functions in two directions (Y- and Z-direction) remarkably influence the fatigue life of notched specimen due to the overlapping of resonance frequency bands of “bending” normal stresses $s_1(t), s_2(t)$ and “torsional” shear stress $s_4(t)$.

Table 4

As an example, the corresponding stress PSD matrices at the verification point under test No.1 (coherence = 0, phase shift = 0°), No.2 (coherence = 0.99, phase shift = 0°) and No.3 (coherence = 0.99, phase shift = 45°) are shown in **Figure 12**, where it can be intuitively observed that coherence

and phase shift between the ASD functions in two directions influence the stress component correlation coefficients.

Figure 12

According to Eqs (17) and (18), the standard deviations of the stress components $s_1(t)$, $s_2(t)$ and $s_4(t)$ are equal to $\sqrt{C_{11}} = 37.2\text{MPa}$, $\sqrt{C_{22}} = 131.4\text{MPa}$ and $\sqrt{C_{44}} = 55.9\text{MPa}$ under test No.1 to No.3. The stress component correlation coefficients are $r_{12} = 1$, $r_{14} = 0$, $r_{24} = 0$ and $r_{12} = 1$, $r_{14} = 0.31$, $r_{24} = 0.31$ under test No.1 and No.2, respectively, whereas the stress component correlation coefficients are $r_{12} = 1$, $r_{14} = 0.54$, $r_{24} = 0.54$ under test No.3. The normal stresses $s_1(t)$ and $s_2(t)$ are always proportional under test No.1 to No.3, because they are produced simultaneously once the bending mode of the testing equipment (including the notched specimen) is excited. Under test No.1 to No.3, the stress component correlation coefficients are really influenced by the coherence and phase shift between the ASD functions in two directions. Moreover, the fatigue lives are thus influenced.

However, by comparing test No.1, No.4, No.7 and test No.8, No.11 in **Table 4**, it is found that the coherence between the ASD functions in two directions has no influence on the fatigue lives when the phase shift is equal to 90° . This behaviour is due to the fact that, when the phase shift is equal to 90° , the generated acceleration random time-domain signals in two directions are fully non-proportional regardless of the coherence between the ASD functions in two directions. Hence, the stress component correlation coefficients are not influenced, and thus the fatigue lives are not influenced.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the time-domain critical plane-based Carpinteri et al. criterion is combined together with the point method of the TCD in order to implement the vibration fatigue analysis of circumferentially notched specimens subjected to coupled multiaxial random vibration environments.

A novel testing equipment with first two order modal frequencies very close to each other is devised, meanwhile biaxial random vibration environment fatigue test is implemented to investigate how coherence and phase shift between the ASD functions in different directions influence the notched specimen fatigue life. It can be pointed out that, when the bending modal frequency is very close to the torsional one, the main resonance frequency bands of “bending” normal stresses $s_1(t)$, $s_2(t)$ and “torsional” shear stress $s_4(t)$ are overlapped. Consequently, coherence and phase shift between the ASD functions in different directions have a remarkable influence on the stress component correlation coefficients and then on the notched specimens’ fatigue lives.

The extended version of the time-domain Carpinteri et al. criterion is validated by means of the comparison with experimental data coming both from the present experimental campaign and another one available in the literature. Good agreement with experimental data (with only two exceptions) confirms the accuracy of the proposed procedure. As a matter of fact, the mean square error T_{RMS} for the examined experimental tests is lower than 2.5.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the China Scholarship Council (Grant

No.201906830093) and the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research (MIUR), Research Grant PRIN 2017 No.2017HFPKZY on “Modelling of constitutive laws for traditional and innovative building materials”.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Z.B.L. and H.H.C conceived, designed and performed the experiments; C.R. and Z.B.L. analyzed the experimental data; S.V. and C.R. proposed the methodology; Z.B.L wrote the original manuscript; S.V., C.R., H.H.C. and A.C. reviewed and revised the manuscript; H.H.C. provided the funding.

REFERENCES

- [1] Habtour E, Choi C, Osterman M, Dasgupta A. Novel approach to improve electronics reliability in the next generation of US army small unmanned ground vehicles under complex vibration conditions. *J Fail Anal Preven.* 2012; 12: 86-95.
- [2] Roberts C, Ewins D. Multi-axis vibration testing of an aerodynamically excited structure. *J Vibr Control.* 2018; 24: 427-437.
- [3] D'Elia G, Mucchi E. Comparison of single-input single-output and multi-input multi-output control strategies for performing sequential single-axis random vibration control test. *J Vibr Control.* 2020; 26: 1988-2000.
- [4] Paulus M, Dasgupta A, Habtour E. Life estimation model of a cantilevered beam subjected to complex random vibration. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct.* 2012; 35: 1058-1070.
- [5] Ernst M, Habtour E, Dasgupta A, Pohland M, Robeson M, Paulus M. Comparison of electronic component durability under uniaxial and multiaxial random vibrations. *J Electron Packag.* 2015; 137: 011009 (8 pages).
- [6] Mršnik M, Slavič J, Boltežar M. Multiaxial vibration fatigue—A theoretical and experimental comparison. *Mech Syst Sign Process.* 2016; 76: 409-423.
- [7] Palmieri M, Česnik M, Slavič J, Cianetti F, Boltežar M. Non-Gaussianity and non-stationarity in vibration fatigue. *Int J Fatigue.* 2017; 97: 9-19.
- [8] Vantadori S, Haynes R, Fortese G, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Zanichelli A. Methodology for assessing embryonic cracks development in structures under high-cycle multiaxial random vibrations. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct.* 2018; 41: 20-28.
- [9] Ogrinec P, Slavič J, Česnik M, Boltežar M. Vibration fatigue at half-sine impulse excitation in the time and frequency domains. *Int J Fatigue.* 2019; 123: 308-317.
- [10] Li Z, Ince A. A unified frequency domain fatigue damage modeling approach for random-on-random spectrum. *Int J Fatigue.* 2019; 124: 123-137.
- [11] Luo Z, Chen H, He X. Influences of correlations between biaxial random vibrations on the fatigue lives of notched metallic specimens. *Int J Fatigue.* 2020: 105730.
- [12] Luo Z, Chen H, Zheng R, Zheng W. A damage gradient model for fatigue life prediction of notched metallic structures under multiaxial random vibrations. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct.*

2020; 43: 2101– 2115

- [13] Lalanne C. *Mechanical Vibration and Shock Analysis, Specification Development*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, USA; 2013.
- [14] MIL-STD-810G, Test Method Standard: Environmental Engineering Considerations and Laboratory Tests, United States Department of Defense, 2008.
- [15] ISO 16750-3, Road Vehicles—Environmental Conditions and Testing for Electrical and Electronic Equipment, International Organization for Standardization, 2012.
- [16] Smallwood DO, Paez TL. A frequency domain method for the generation of partially coherent normal stationary time domain signals. *Shock Vibr.* 1993; 1: 45-53.
- [17] Underwood MA, Keller T, Ayres R. Multi-shaker control a review of the evolving state-of-the-art. *Sound Vibr.* 2017; 51: 8-16.
- [18] Zheng R, Chen H, Vandepitte D, Luo Z. Multi-exciter stationary non-Gaussian random vibration test with time domain randomization. *Mech Syst Sign Process.* 2019; 122: 103-116.
- [19] Carpinteri A, Fortese G, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Vantadori S. Spectral fatigue life estimation for non-proportional multiaxial random loading. *Theor Appl Fract Mech.* 2016, 83: 67-72.
- [20] Vantadori S, Carpinteri A, Fortese G, Ronchei C. Influence of random fatigue loading non-proportionality on damage. *Theor Appl Fract Mech.* 2018, 96: 56–63
- [21] Zhu SP, Yu ZY, Correia J, De Jesus A, Berto F. Evaluation and comparison of critical plane criteria for multiaxial fatigue analysis of ductile and brittle materials. *Int J Fatigue.* 2018; 112: 279-288
- [22] Neuber H. *Theory of Notch Stresses: Principles for Exact Stress Calculation*. JW Edwards, Ann Arbor, USA; 1946.
- [23] Peterson RE. *Notch sensitivity*. New York: McGraw Hill; 1959: 293–306.
- [24] Tanaka K. Engineering formulae for fatigue strength reduction due to crack-like notches. *Int J Fract.* 1983; 22: R39-R46.
- [25] Lazzarin P, Tovo R, Meneghetti G. Fatigue crack initiation and propagation phases near notches in metals with low notch sensitivity. *Int J Fatigue.* 1997; 19: 647-657.
- [26] Taylor D. Geometrical effects in fatigue: a unifying theoretical model. *Int J Fatigue.* 1999; 21: 413-420.

- [27] El Haddad MH, Topper TH, Smith KN. Prediction of non propagating cracks. *Eng Fract Mech.* 1979; 11: 573-584.
- [28] Taylor D, Wang G. The validation of some methods of notch fatigue analysis. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct.* 2000; 23: 387-394.
- [29] Bellett D, Taylor D, Marco S, Mazzeo E, Guillois J, Pircher T. The fatigue behaviour of three-dimensional stress concentrations. *Int J Fatigue.* 2005; 27: 207-221.
- [30] Vantadori S, Iturrioz I, Ronchei C. Discussion on fatigue life estimation under multiaxial random loading: Comparison between time-and frequency-domain approach. *Theor Appl Fract Mech.* 2018; 96: 134-145.
- [31] Carpinteri A, Fortese G, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Spagnoli A, Vantadori S. Fatigue life evaluation of metallic structures under multiaxial random loading. *Int J Fatigue.* 2016; 90: 191-199.
- [32] Carpinteri A, Vantadori S, Łagoda T, Karolczuk A, Kurek M, Ronchei C. Fatigue assessment of metallic components under uniaxial and multiaxial variable amplitude loading. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct.* 2018; 41: 1306-1317.
- [33] Vantadori S, Iturrioz I, Carpinteri A, Greco F, Ronchei C. A novel procedure for damage evaluation of fillet-welded joints. *Int J Fatigue.* 2020; 136: 105599.
- [34] Maia NMM, Silva JMM. *Theoretical and Experimental Modal Analysis.* Springer Science, Sesimbra, Portugal, 1998.
- [35] Yam LY, Leung TP, Li DB, Xue KZ. Theoretical and experimental study of modal strain analysis. *J Sound Vibr.* 1996; 191: 251-260.
- [36] Füllekrug U. Utilization of multi-axial shaking tables for the modal identification of structures. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Ser A: Math Phys Eng Sci.* 2001; 359(1786): 1753-1770.
- [37] Skibicki, D. *Phenomena and Computational Models of Non-Proportional Fatigue of Materials,* Springer: London, UK, 2014.
- [38] Paulus M, Doughty K. Effect of resonant frequency shifting on time to failure of a cantilevered beam under vibration. *J IEST.* 2010; 53: 59-68.
- [39] Susmel L, Taylor D. *The Theory of Critical Distances as an alternative experimental strategy*

for the determination of K_{Ic} and ΔK_{th} . *Eng Fract Mech.* 2010; 77: 1492-1501.

[40] Vantadori, S, Carpinteri, A, Fortese, G, Ronchei, C, Scorza, D, Zanichelli, A. Fatigue lifetime evaluation of notched components: Implementation of the control volume concept in a strain-based LCF criterion. *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics* 2018, 97, 400-408.

Nomenclature

\mathbf{C}_v	stress covariance matrix
C_{ii}, C_{ij}	diagonal and non-diagonal elements of \mathbf{C}_v
$\mathbf{F}(t)$	force excitation vector
$\mathbf{G}_a(f)$	one-sided acceleration PSD matrix
$G_{kk}(f), G_{kl}(f)$	diagonal and non-diagonal elements of $\mathbf{G}_a(f)$
$\mathbf{G}_s(f)$	one-sided stress PSD matrix
$\mathbf{H}_d(\omega)$	displacement FRF matrix
$\mathbf{H}_s(\omega)$	stress FRF matrix under force excitation vector
$\mathbf{H}_{as}(\omega), \mathbf{H}_{as}(f)$	stress FRF matrices under acceleration excitation vector
k_{axi}	fully-reversed uniaxial $S-N$ curve's inverse slope
$K_{t,b}, K_{t,t}$	stress concentration factors for bending and torsion
L	characteristic length of material
m_r, k_r, c_r, f_r	r -th modal parameters
$\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{C}$	modal parameter matrices
$\mathbf{N}(t)$	normal stress vector
Puvw	Cartesian coordinate frame connected with the critical plane
PXYZ	fixed Cartesian coordinate frame
$\hat{P}\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}$	Cartesian coordinate frame corresponding to averaged principal stress directions
$\mathbf{q}(t)$	modal coordinate vector
$r_{ij}, r_{12}, r_{14}, r_{24}$	correlation coefficients between stress components
$\mathbf{R}(t)$	shear stress vector

$s_i(t), s_j(t)$	stress components
$\mathbf{S}_n(t)$	stress vector acting on the critical plane at point P_{cr}
$T_{exp,ave}, T_{cal}$	averaged experimental and calculated fatigue lives
\mathbf{T}	constant transformation matrix
$\mathbf{u}(t)$	vector form of absolute displacement
$\mathbf{v}(t)$	vector form of relative displacement
$\ddot{\mathbf{w}}(t)$	vector form of acceleration random excitation
$V(t)$	weight function
Φ	displacement modal shape matrix
Φ^s	stress modal shape matrix
δ	off-angle
$\varphi(t), \theta(t), \phi(t)$	instantaneous values of Euler angles
$\hat{\varphi}, \hat{\theta}, \hat{\phi}$	weighted averaged values of Euler angles
$\sigma_s(t)$	stress vector
$\sigma_1(t)$	maximum principal stress
$\sigma_{af,-1}, \tau_{af,-1}$	fatigue limits of the fully-reversed uniaxial and torsional $S-N$ curves
$\sigma_{eq,a,k}$	amplitude of equivalent stress for the k -th reversal
$\gamma_{kl}^2(f), \theta_{kl}(f)$	coherence and phase shift between the ASD functions in two directions
ω	pulsation

Acronyms

ASD	auto-spectral density
CSD	cross-spectral density
FEM	finite element method
FRF	frequency response function

MDOF	multi-degree-of-freedom
PSD	power spectral density
RFC	rain-flow counting
TCD	theory of critical distance

Figure 1. Notched metallic structural component: determination of the verification point.

Figure 2. Novel testing equipment: (a) schematic representation, and (b) picture.

Figure 3. Triaxial shaker table.

Figure 4. Specimen geometry (size in mm).

Table 1. Mechanical and fatigue properties of 2024-T4 aluminum alloy [11].

PROPERTY	
Density	2780 kg/m ³
Young's modulus	73 GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.33
Yield strength	400 MPa
Ultimate tension strength	545 MPa
Inverse slope of fully-reversed uniaxial fatigue curve, k_{axi}	8.9
Fully-reversed normal strength at N_0 loading cycles	165 MPa
Fully-reversed torsional strength at N_0 loading cycles	119 MPa

Table 2. Modal testing results.

MODAL ORDER	1	2
Modal frequency [Hz]	80.5	82.5
Modal damping ratio [%]	0.9	1.1
Vibration mode	Bending	Torsion

Figure 5. ASD functions: (a) excitation in Y-direction; (b) excitation in Z-direction.

Figure 6. Excitations: (a) coherence; (b) phase shift.

Figure 7. Acceleration vs time: (a) along Y-direction; (b) along Z-direction; (c) their combination.

Table 3. Biaxial and uniaxial random vibration environment fatigue tests: loading conditions.

Test No.	Max G_{yy} [g ² /Hz]	Max G_{zz} [g ² /Hz]	Coherence	Phase shift [°]	T_{exp} [s]	$T_{exp,ave}$ [s]
1	0.009	0.009	0	0	2200	2093
					2190	
					1890	
2	0.009	0.009	0.99	0	4260	4240
					4560	
					3900	
3	0.009	0.009	0.99	45	6390	8100
					8490	
					9420	
4	0.009	0.009	0.99	90	1800	2100
					2040	
					2460	
5	0.009	0.009	0.5	0	2580	3080
					3390	
					3270	
6	0.009	0.009	0.5	45	5790	6040
					6360	
					5970	
7	0.009	0.009	0.5	90	2310	2160
					1740	
					2430	
8	0.01	0.005	0	0	5490	4920
					4470	
					4800	
9	0.01	0.005	0.9	0	9360	9190
					9810	
					8400	
10	0.01	0.005	0.99	45	22080	20970
					19860	
11	0.01	0.005	0.99	90	6030	5250
					3990	
					5730	
12	0.0065	0.0065	0	0	9120	8190
					7200	
					8250	
13	0.02	-	-	-	1380	2090
					2880	
					2010	
14	-	0.015	-	-	2070	2020
					2490	
					1500	

Figure 8. Finite element model: testing equipment and specimen.

Figure 9. Modal analysis: (a) bending mode (80.8 Hz); (b) torsional mode (83.2 Hz).

Figure 10. Comparison between numerical and experimental acceleration FRFs at: (a) T-clamping component end (under random acceleration base excitation in Y-direction); (b) specimen end (under random acceleration base excitation in Z-direction).

Figure 11. Comparison between calculated fatigue lives determined by employing the proposed procedure and averaged experimental fatigue lives reported: (a) in the present paper; (b) in Refs [11,12].

Table 4. Stress components with different correlation coefficients at the verification point and experimental fatigue lives under different loading cases.

Test No.	$\sqrt{C_{11}}$ [MPa]	$\sqrt{C_{22}}$ [MPa]	$\sqrt{C_{44}}$ [MPa]	Correlation coeff. r_{12}	Correlation coeff. r_{14}, r_{24}	T_{exp} [s]	$T_{exp,ave}$ [s]
1	37.2	131.4	55.9	1	0	2200	2093
						2190	
						1890	
2	37.2	131.4	55.9	1	0.31	4260	4240
						4560	
						3900	
3	37.2	131.4	55.9	1	0.54	6390	8100
						8490	
						9420	
4	37.2	131.4	55.9	1	0	1800	2100
						2040	
						2460	
5	37.2	131.4	55.9	1	0.22	2580	3080
						3390	
						3270	
6	37.2	131.4	55.9	1	0.38	5790	6040
						6360	
						5970	
7	37.2	131.4	55.9	1	0	2310	2160
						1740	
						2430	
8	27.7	97.9	58.9	1	0	5490	4920
						4470	
						4800	
9	27.7	97.9	58.9	1	0.31	9360	9190
						9810	
						8400	
10	27.7	97.9	58.9	1	0.54	22080	20970
						19860	
						6030	
11	27.7	97.9	58.9	1	0	3990	5250
						5730	
						9120	
12	31.6	111.7	47.5	1	0	7200	8190
						8250	
						1380	
13	-	-	83.3	-	-	2880	2090
						2010	
						2070	
14	48.0	169.6	-	1	-	2490	2020
						1500	

Continue

Figure 12. Response stress PSD matrices at the verification point under:
 (a) test No. 1, (b) No. 2, and (c) No. 3.